

HISTORY TEACHERS' VIEWS ON USING LOCAL HISTORYⁱ

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Abstract:

Local history should be taught in history courses. It enables students to investigate and learn geography, form connections between past and present, and gain important life skills. This study analyzes the views and practices of Turkish history teachers vis-a-vis local histories in a qualitative study. The focus group consisted of 12 history teachers working in the central provinces of Kayseri city. Researchers used semi-structured interviews to collect data, and used qualitative analysis, explanatory and deductive codes to explore emerging patterns in the data. Our data show that local history lessons facilitate greater knowledge of local geography and culture. Conversely, teachers reported financial issues, lower teaching hours, and disinterested students when implementing local history curricula. According to these results, our researchers provide recommendations to better implement local history activities in the classroom.

Keywords: History teaching, local history, teachers

1. Introduction

History education in Turkey has failed for years to meet standards and has been a target of criticism (Avci Akcali & Aslan, 2016, p. 377). A major issue is that the teaching curriculum is based on a constructivist approach to education systems and is based on rote-learning. Rote memorization is used even for developing chronological thinking skills, historical comprehension skills, forming cause and effect relationship skills, perceiving change and continuity skills, research skills based on historical questioning, historical analysis and commenting skills, analysis of historical problem, decision making skills, viewing past from perspective of historical people, and developing empathy (History Class Curriculum, 2018a).

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History curricula are prepared based on a constructivist approach in Turkey including practices such as oral history, local history and family history as well as related research tasks assigned to students related with local history based on class content. By enabling students to relate local history to recent past and national history, national consciousness and history sensitivity may be achieved (TTKB, 2007; 2008a; 2008b; 2009; 2010; MEB, 2018b). Although there is already guidance regarding local and oral histories in the curriculum, there are problems when these recommendations are adapted to the teaching process (Avcı Akcalı & Aslan, 2016, p. 377; Demircioğlu, 2010).

Local history should be included in history education so that students may teaching investigate and learn relevant geographies, form connections between past and present, and gain important life skills based on these connections. To do that, we must first understand what “local history” means.

There are multiple definitions regarding local history. For example, Rogers (1977, p. 4) defines local history as “*analysing development of certain local unit as a society within their historical context and by comparing with similar units*” and stated that history of a family or village, story of a business or channel, story of certain area, property, field or house on certain period of time can be considered under local history (Rogers, 1977, p. 1). Other definitions regarding local history are as follow:

- A road that enables enjoyable interest to humans and enables awareness (Hoskins, 1984, p.5),
- Story of a state, rural area, a province, a city or other local area or history of people in that area or story of what is local (Calkin, 1942, p. 53),
- Connecting people and space in political power focus (Danacıoğlu, 2001a, p. 6),
- Orientation from national richness to local richness (Aslan, 2000, p. 195),

In addition to these definitions, Ilyasoglu (2001, p. 38) relates local history with people, the experiences of these people, the history of these experiences and how these experiences are collected in people’s memories and transferred through generations. To help students understand how these developments occur and how they affect our lives (Demircioğlu, 2010) more effectively, history teachers must include local history activities in history class curricula. Accordingly, it is recommended that teachers organise virtual museum visits, historical and museum trips, and other local opportunities if possible (History Class Curriculum, 2018a).

2. Purpose

This study was conducted to identify views of Turkish history teachers towards local history and local history curricula. Accordingly, answers for the following questions were investigated:

What is the level of history teachers in:

- Knowledge and awareness of local history?
- Self-sufficiency and perception about local history?
- Attitude towards local history?
- Views regarding local history in education?

3. Method

3.1. Model of Study

In this study where views of history teachers towards local history teaching are analysed, qualitative methods are followed to express events in realistic and holistic way within natural environments (Islamoglu, 2009; Yildirim and Simsek, 2008).

3.2. Study Group

Study groups of this study are based on convenient sampling among purposeful sampling to easily select people and groups to work on (Sonmez & Alacapinar, 2014). Data regarding history teachers as study group of this study are presented in the table below.

Table 1: Study Group

Gender	Seniority				Total
	0-5 years	6-10 years	11-15 years	16-20 years	
Female	1	4	2		7
Male	1	3		1	5
Total	2	7	2	1	12

Among history teachers, 7 were female and 5 were male. In terms of seniority, the study group consisted of teachers with various levels of experience. Two had between 0-5 years, 7 had between 6-10 years, 2 had between 11-15 years and 1 had more than 16 years of experience.

4. Data Collection Tool and Data Analysis

Based on purpose of this study, we also employed interview techniques enabling a more in-depth form of information collected (Buyukozturk et al., 2010). Data were collected with a semi-structured interview form that enabled individuals to react freely (Erkus, 2009).

Interview questions were prepared in an open, clear and unguided way to uncover emotions and opinions of history teachers towards local history lessons. Later, expert opinions were collected for these questions and necessary corrections were made. Additionally, to test whether these statements were suitable for interview groups, pilot interviews were conducted with two history teachers, and questions were edited based on these interviews and prepared for application. The form consisted of a total of 13 questions with 9 open-ended and 4 close-ended (questions 3, 4, 6 and 7) questions. Interview questions were categorised to identify history teachers' information and awareness of local history, self-sufficiency perceptions and attitudes, and to collect views regarding application. Sub-problems of this study form main categories of interview questions. Interview questions and main categories (sub-problems) are given in Table 2.

Table 2: Interview questions and main categories

Main categories	Interview questions
Knowledge and awareness about local history teaching	1. What does local history teaching recall? 2. Which properties should local history teaching activities have? 3. Have you received any education towards local history teaching during your undergraduate education?
Self-sufficiency perception about local history teaching	4. Do you think you are sufficient about local history teaching? 5. Which qualities do history teachers should have for effective local history teaching?
Attitude towards local history teaching in teaching process	6. Should local history teaching be included in history classes? 7. Do you include local history teaching in teaching process? 8. What are the benefits of including local history teaching activities in teaching process?
Views regarding local history teaching application	9. Which activities can be organised under local history teaching in teaching process? 10. What are methods and techniques that can be applied in local history teaching? 11. Which points do you consider in local history teaching? 12. What are the problems in local history teaching? 13. Which recommendations can you make to achieve desired efficiency from local history teaching activities?

Approximately 15 minutes interviews were conducted in teachers' rooms or deputy head of school rooms. During interviews an appropriate atmosphere was created for teachers to answer comfortably. Teachers' answers during interviews were recorded with a recording device.

The data obtained were transcribed and analysed. To explain qualitative data and to find relationships, explanatory and deductive codes are used. To ensure reliability of coding, coherence percentage of coding by two researchers was calculated as 84%. Researchers tried to express common ideas on inconsistent data sections.

Codes and findings obtained in this study were presented without any comments and by direct quotations in way to be clear for readers. Teachers were coded as T1, T2, T3, T4.

5. Findings, comments and discussions

5.1 Local history teaching perception of history teachers

Views of history teachers towards using local history in the teaching process are presented in the table below.

Table 3: Local history teaching perception of history teachers

Local history teaching perception of history teachers	f
Learning history of place they live (T1, T2, T3, T4, T5, T6, T9, T10)	8
Enabling connection from past to present (T2, T9, T12)	3
Transferring historical heritage (T7, T9)	2

Enabling connection from far to near (T8, T11)	2
Having trips-observation (T6)	1
Enabling reaching from regional history understanding to national history understanding (T8)	1

History teachers were asked what local history teaching made them recall. As seen from the table created based on collected answers, it can be seen that history teachers mainly emphasised learning history of where they live, enabling connection from past to future, ensuring transfer of historical heritage, and ensuring connection from near too far. Additionally, it was stated that they aimed to reach from regional history understanding to national history understanding. Examples from history teachers' statements are given below:

“Our geography has connection from past to present. History of our region is important in terms of effects of what past civilisations contribute to today.” (T2).

“It is reaching from regional history understanding to national history understanding based on our close surrounding” (T8).

“It acts like bridge between people who lived in the past and people living now. We are transferring of history of our surrounding to next generations...” (T9).

5.2 Views of history teachers on the nature of local history activities

Below, a table indicating views of history teachers on properties that local history teaching activities should have is presented.

Table 4: Views on properties that local history teaching activities should have

Properties local history teaching activities should have	f
Being interesting (T2, T3, T6, T9, T11, T12)	6
Learning historical and geographical properties of region they live in (T1, T4)	2
Providing information about culture of region they live in (T1, T4)	2
Accessibility (T11, T12)	2
Other* (T3, T5, T6, T7, T8, T9, T10, T11, T12)	9

*Having application area, thinking together with learner, achieving research and common emotions, related with curriculum, being economic, learning by going living, based on constructive approach, exciting students, triggering awareness, suitability for student's age, trip and analysing, analysing, not boring student, attracting attention.

History teachers were asked for properties that local history activities should contain. As seen from the table created based on collected answers, history teachers expressed

that local history activities should be interesting, ensure learning of historical and geographical region they live in, providing information about culture of region they live in and easy access to local history teaching activities locations. Examples from history teachers' statements are given below:

"I want introductory properties based on historical and geographical properties of the region. I want them to have information about the culture of that region such as marriage, birth, funerals" (T1).

"I am careful about being interesting, not boring the student and being accessible" (T11).

"Interesting, attractive, accessible..." (T12).

5.3 Education of history teachers on local history teaching during undergraduate education

The table below shows whether or not history teachers received education on local history teaching during their undergraduate education.

Table 5: Table for education of history teachers on local history teaching during undergraduate education

Education for local history teaching	f
Not received (T1, T2, T3, T4, T5, T8, T9, T10, T11, T12)	10
Received (T6, T7)	2

History teachers were asked whether they received education on local history teaching during undergraduate education. It was seen that teachers had not received education on local history teaching. Examples of history teachers' views are presented:

"I haven't received any education on local history teaching during undergraduate education" (T1).

"No, I haven't received a class for local history teaching" (T3).

"I received a class within formation education..." (T6).

5.3 Self-sufficiency levels of history teachers in local history teaching

Self-sufficiency levels of history teachers in local history teaching during teaching process are presented in a table below.

Table 6: Self-sufficiency levels of history teachers in local history teaching

Self-sufficiency levels of history teachers in local history teaching	f
Sufficient (T6, T8)	2
Partially sufficient (T5, T7, T12)	3
Insufficient (T1, T2, T3, T4, T9, T10, T11)	7

History teachers were asked whether they regarded themselves sufficient in local history teaching. Based on collected answers, it was seen that most of the history teachers believed they were insufficient, and many of the history teachers that believed they were partially sufficient. Examples of history teachers' views are presented:

"Actually I am not sufficient. Because we shortly talk about this topic as it is not in the curriculum. But as a historian, I can provide information as I work in my hometown" (T1).

"I am insufficient as I have not received any education in this field" (T3).

"Yes, I am sufficient" (T8).

"Although I have better opportunities than many other schools, I believe I am insufficient" (T10).

5.4 Views of history teachers on properties that teachers should have for effective local history teaching

Table that shows views of history teachers towards the characteristics they require for effective local history education are presented.

Table 7: Views of history teachers towards characteristics that history teachers need for effective local history teaching

Characteristics of history teachers	f
Knowledge of local history (T2, T3, T5, T8, T12)	5
Educated (T1, T3, T4)	3
Researcher (T2, T9, T11)	3
Loving occupation (T5, T11, T12)	3
Having resources (T1, T4)	2
Being a good observer (T6, T11)	2
Knowing student (T6, T11)	2

Activating student (T7, T11)	2
Knowing environment well (T11, T12)	2
Other* (T2, T5, T6, T9, T10)	5

*transferring knowledge, preparing for process, development of social skills, using time effectively, attracting attention of student, working without getting bored, being planned, being organised.

History teachers were asked about properties that history teachers should have for effective local history teaching. Based on the answers collected, the majority of history teachers stated that teachers must be knowledgeable about local history, while some stated that teachers must be educated, well-researched, and love their occupation. Additionally, it was stated that history teachers must have related resources, be good observers, know students, activate students and know their environment. Examples from history teachers' statements are given below:

"Teachers must know the geography and history of that region. Teachers must be researchers, and transfer this to the student during in-class activities" (T2).

"Teachers must have good observation skills, use time effectively, select topics to attract attention of students, understand students and spirit of the space" (T6).

"Teachers must be researchers, know the surrounding environment, and guide students accordingly. Teacher must have good observation skills. Teacher must activate students. Teacher must have love for the occupation and the occupation must not be drudgery..." (T11).

5.5 Views of history teachers towards including local history teaching in teaching process

All of the history teachers stated that local history should be included in teaching process. A table showing the views of history teachers towards including local history in teaching process is presented below.

Table 8: Views of history teachers towards including local history teaching in the teaching process

Including local history teaching in history class	f
It should be included (T1, T2, T3, T4, T5, T6, T7, T8, T9, T10, T11, T12)	12
It should not be included	-

History teachers were asked whether local history teaching should be included in the teaching process and provide explanations. All history teachers expressed that local history teaching activities should be offered in classes. Examples of history teachers' views are presented:

"Yes, it can be used. I believe this can increase success in history classes. It can attract attention of students" (T3).

"It definitely must be included in history class. At least three weeks of the year must be on this topic. Cities should be considered under the 'Tombstones are mirrors of the past' approach" (T6).

"Yes, just giving the information from the course book makes students bored. This decreases monotony and ensures active participation of student. Also, it ensures permanent learning by giving time based on activity type. They can link conditions of that period with current conditions" (T11).

5.7 Including local history teaching in teaching process by history teachers

History teachers were asked whether they included local history teaching in the teaching process. Based on answers collected, history teachers' views are presented in table.

Table 9: Table for including local history teaching in teaching process by history teachers

Including local history teaching and frequency		f
Yes	Frequently (T8)	1
	Sometimes (T1, T4, T5)	3
	Rarely (T2, T3, T6, T7, T10, T11, T12)	7
No	Never (T9)	1

History teachers were asked for including local history teaching in teaching process by history teachers and frequency. The majority of history teachers stated that local history is important in the teaching process. Examples of history teachers' views are presented:

"Sometimes, I am especially including local history teaching in culture classes. I especially include historical places" (T1).

"Sometimes, I only provide information about Karum tablets when talking about Hittite in 9th grade ancient history" (T2).

"I do but in limited way. Because time and curriculum don't let me" (T6).

5.8 Benefits of including local history teaching in the teaching process

Table showing views of history teachers towards the benefits of including local history in teaching process are presented below.

Table 10: Views of history teachers towards the benefits of including local history in teaching process

Benefits of including local history teaching in teaching process	f
Learning history of place they live (T1, T2, T4, T5, T6, T7)	6
Contributing to general knowledge (T1, T4, T5, T8)	4
Ensuring permanent learning (T9, S10, T11, T12)	4
Being interesting (T3, T5)	2
Knowing the city (T6, T1)	2
Connecting with past (T6, T11)	2
Ensuring cultural transfer (T7, T8)	2
Preventing class to become boring (T9, T12)	2
Other* (T3, T5, T10, T11)	4

*Making topic important, attracting attention, increasing interest, enabling class participation, being effective, increasing love towards region they live in, learning lessons.

History teachers were asked about the benefits of including local history in the teaching process. History teachers stated that the teaching of local history is beneficial to learning the histories of where they live, as well as beneficial for permanent learning and general knowledge. Some history teachers stated that in addition to being fun, local history teaching helped students to better know their cities, connect with past, ensure cultural transfer and prevent class from being boring. Examples from history teachers' statements are given below:

"People can contribute to general knowledge by knowing history of where they live and where they are. If we know our local history, we can better grasp our general history" (T1).

"Students have less or more interest to geography they live in. I believe that being aware of history right next to them will help understanding our rooted history that goes back to Central Asia, form basis for interest and increase interest and participation to class..." (T5).

"You can have permanent learning, know properties of the geography you are in and make a connection between past and present by learning lessons" (T11).

5.9 Activities that can be organised for teaching local history

History teachers were asked what type of activities can be organised related to local history teaching. Based on collected answers, history teachers' views are presented in table.

Table 11: Activities that can be organised under local history teaching

Activities that can be organised under local history teaching	f
Trip (T1, T3, T4, T5, T6, T7, T10, T11, T12)	9
Historical play (T9, T10, T12)	3
*Others (T2, T5, T6, T7, T8, T12)	6

*Project homework, research homework, model making, using libraries, exhibitions, museum visits, historical role playing.

History teachers were asked which activities can be organised under local history teaching in teaching process. History teachers stated that organising trips, historical plays, project homework, research homework, model making, using libraries, exhibitions, museum visits, historical role playing can be organised under local history teaching. Examples from history teachers' statements are given below:

"We can organise museum trips. While talking about a chiefdom, artefacts of that chiefdom in the region can be given as example. History of where they are can be explained. Historical plays can be made" (T10).

"Museum trips, plays, historical role playing" (T12).

5.10 Methods and techniques that can be applied in local history teaching

Answers of history teachers regarding methods and techniques that can be applied in local history teaching are given in the table below.

Table 12: Views of history teachers on methods and techniques that can be applied in local history teaching

Methods and techniques that can be applied in local history teaching	f
Trip (T1, T3, T4, T5, T6, T7, T8, T9, T10, T11, T12)	11
Interview (T7, T8, T9, T11, T12)	5
Narrating (T1, T4, T5, T7, T10)	5
Argumentation (T2, T5, T11, T12)	4
Exhibition (T1, T4, T2, T8)	4
Conference (T1, T4, T8)	3

Research (T5, T8, T10)	3
Seminar (T1, T4)	2
Question-answer (T6, T10)	2
Other* (T5, T6, T7, T10, T12)	5

*Discussion, observation, drama, project

History teachers were asked which methods and techniques could be used in local history education. The majority of history teachers stated that trips, interviews, narration and argumentation techniques could be used. Additionally, they stated that exhibition, conference, research, seminar and question-answer methods and techniques could be used. Examples from history teachers' statements are given below:

"Narrating, trip, conference, seminar, exhibition" (T1).

"One-to-one question-answers, trips and observations are the best methods" (T6).

"Trips, analysis, narrating, question-answer, drama" (T10).

5.11 Things that are considered during local history teaching

History teachers were asked which things should be considered in local history lessons. Based on collected answers, history teachers' views are presented in the table below.

Table 13: History teachers' views on things to consider during local history teaching

Things that are considered during local history teaching	f
Providing preliminary information to students (T2, T5, T9, T10, T12)	5
Gaining preliminary information by teachers (T5, T9, T10, T11, T12)	5
Making the activity fun (T3, T5)	2
Other* (T2, T5, T6, T7, T8, T10, T12)	7

*Planning, giving homework, making the activity motivating, ensuring participation during activity, making activity about topic, motivating students with the activities, compliance with purpose, activity being entertaining.

History teachers were asked which things should be considered local history teaching in the teaching process. The majority of history teachers stated that both students and teachers should have preliminary information and activities should be fun for students. Examples from history teachers' statements are given below:

"Topics that will attract attention of students can be included" (T3).

"I make sure both I and my students have basic knowledge on this topic. I attract attention and create an education environment with high student motivation and where they can contribute to process..." (T5).

"I tried to start explaining the topic to attract attention of student. I try to provide historical information when I organise trip. When we visit other regions with our students, I try to have preliminary work and inform students ..." (T10).

5.12 Problems in local history teaching

Problems experienced by history teachers during local history teaching are presented in the table below.

Table 14: Problems experienced by history teachers during local history teaching

Problems	f
Management barrier (T2, T9, T11, T12)	4
Procedures (T5, T9, T11, T12)	4
Financial problems (T5, T7, T10)	3
Lack of time (T6, T7, T9)	3
Disinterest of children (T7, T8)	2
Exclusion from the curriculum (T3, T6)	2
No problems (T1, T4)	2
Other* (T3, T5, T7, T8, T9, T11, T12)	7

*Disobeying students, corporate problems, lack of coordination, lack of material, lack of environmental awareness, lack of resources, damaged historical artefacts, problems with preliminary work, families not wanting trips, crowded classes.

History teachers were asked what type of problems they experienced while teaching local history. As seen from table, history teachers expressed problems such as management barriers, problems with permission, financial problems and lack of time to teach. Additionally, there are other problems such as disinterest of children and the exclusion of local history education from the curriculum. Examples from history teachers' statements are given below:

"Most important problems are insufficient opportunities, lack of material, lack of environmental awareness, lack of interest of students on topics, lack of time and lack of importance of local history" (T7).

"Management does not let going outside the class, insufficient class hours, procedures, problems with preliminary work" (T9).

"Families do not like trip locations, school management does not like those trips, and the dominating were problems due to crowded classes and too many procedures." (T11).

5.13 Recommendations to achieve desired efficiency from local history education during the teaching process

Recommendations for history teachers to achieve desired efficiency from local history teaching are presented in the table below.

Table 15: Views of history teachers to achieve desired efficiency from local history teaching

Recommendations	f
Support from school management (T2, T10, T11, T12)	4
Help from municipalities for trips (T1, T4, T11)	3
Teacher education on this topic (T1, T4, T3)	3
Adapting curriculum (T8, T9, T11)	3
Preparing a book about local history for classrooms (T1, T4)	2
Organising handicraft exhibitions (T1, T4)	2
Obtaining resources (T1, T4)	2
Organising trips (T2, T10)	2
Helping grasping importance of local history (T5, T10)	2
Increasing class hours (T11, T12)	2
Other*(T3, T5, T6, T7, T10, T12)	6

*Relating with topic, being process based education, time, permission, student motivation, being interesting, active, preliminary work, plan, parent participation.

History teachers were asked to present recommendations to achieve desired efficiency from local history teaching are presented in the table below. As seen from the table, history teachers recommended support from school management, support from municipalities for trips, teachers having education on this subject, compliance with curriculum, preparing books about local history teaching. Examples from history teachers' statements are given below.

"Municipalities should support these trips, local history books should be prepared for each city and province, handicraft exhibitions should be organised, trainings should be given to teachers, resources should be provided" (T1).

"Allocated time should be more. Official institutions should be informed and students can be more enthusiastic" (T6).

“School management should be explained about importance of this topic and management should care for it. We should try to visit museums especially during museum week. Preparations must be made and students must grasp why this is important” (T10).

6. Results and Discussion

In this study conducted to determine history teachers' use of local history based activities in the teaching process, following results are obtained from findings.

6.1 Results and discussion on knowledge and awareness of history teachers about local history education

In the first sub-problem of the study, answers for knowledge and awareness of history teachers about local history teaching in teaching process are investigated. The first question for this sub-problem is what local history teaching meant for teachers. The majority of history teachers stated that it is about learning history of where they live, while others answered that it must meet the content of this concept. Local history analysis roots, development, lifestyle, social-cultural-economic development of societies lived or living in certain region (Aslan, 2000), the traditions people accumulate in their memory (Ilyasoglu, 2001), history of a state, city or local region or people living in that area (Calkin, 1942, p. 43), an orientation from uniformity of nation to richness of regional (Aslan, 2000) and ensures framework for students to build their own roots or identities (Hawkey, 1995, p. 33). Accordingly, it can be stated that history teachers have awareness about local history education.

In the 2nd question in this sub-problem, history teachers were asked what properties local history education based activities should have. History teachers stated that local history teaching must be interesting (Avci Akcali & Aslan, 2016), students must learn by doing, they must develop the curiosity of students, provide co-working skills (Demircioglu, 2010), and contribute to the development of various skills (Danker, 2005; Quest, 2006), ensuring close cooperation with geography (Slater, 1995, p. 33).

In 3rd question of this sub-problem, history teachers were asked whether they received education on local history in their undergraduate education. The majority of history teachers stated that they had not received local history teaching in their undergraduate education.

Teachers expressed that they had not received local history teaching because using this technique was not provided as separate class, and they had not learned about this technique in teaching principles and methods classes. They cannot remember this technique even if they had education.

6.2 Results and discussion on self-sufficiency perception of history teachers about local history teaching in teaching process

In the second sub-problem of this study, the purpose was to determine self-sufficiency perception of history teachers regarding local history teaching in teaching process.

Related with this sub-problem, history teachers were asked whether they regarded themselves as sufficient in local history teaching. It was seen that there were high number of history teachers who believed they were insufficient and number of history teachers that believed they were only partially sufficient. Aktin, Karakus & Saglam (2013) worked on prospective teachers and stated that prospective teachers believed they were insufficient. In this sense, it can be considered that problem starts at undergraduate education level. Oner (2015) stated that teachers feel insufficient in local history and surrounding environment because it is not effectively used in education faculties with teaching purpose. One of the reasons history teachers feel partially sufficient or insufficient on local history teaching can be considered as lack of local history education during undergraduate education.

Lastly, history teachers were asked about properties that history teachers should have for effective local history teaching. Majority of history teachers stated that teachers must be knowledgeable about local history while some stated that teachers must be educated, researched, and love their jobs. Teachers stated that history teachers must have related resources, be good observers, know students, activate students and know their environments.

Additionally, Ata (2015) stated that history teachers should be aware of material cultural elements in close surrounding of school, know social activity regulation and organise trips based on regulation. As history teachers have all these properties, local history teaching based activities can be completed in more effective manner.

6.3 Results and discussion on attitudes of history teachers about local history education in the teaching process

The third sub-problem of this study investigated attitudes of history teachers about local history teaching. Accordingly, history teachers were asked whether local history teaching should be included in history class. All of history teachers answered that local history teaching should be included in history class. When reasons for this situation were asked, generally teachers expressed that topics in history class are suitable for local history teaching. Metin & Oran (2014) found similar results and stated that majority of teachers used local history teaching based activities in their classes. When richness of cultural and historical heritage environment in our country are considered, it is believed that history teachers can plan well and match these environments with purpose and gains of history class.

History teachers were asked about including local history teaching in teaching process by history teachers and frequency. The majority of history teachers stated that local history activities are included in teaching process. Metin & Oran (2014) found similar results and stated that majority of teachers used local history teaching based activities in their classes.

Lastly, history teachers were asked benefits of including local history teaching in teaching process. History teachers stated that local history teaching is positive for learning the history of where they live, permanent learning, and contributions to general knowledge. By using local history teaching in history classes, it can prevent classes from being boring.

Additionally, a high number of abstract concepts can be concretised and permanence of knowledge can be increased with active participation. It is clear that most effective and permanent learning can be ensured with participation to teaching process (Cetinkaya & Gulmez, 2002). Mainstone & Bryant (1972) stated that when students bring learned knowledge to classroom to share, they will gain experience that can help personal development and understanding of history. Additionally, it was stated that local history teaching develops logical thinking style in students and turn learning to a fun activity (Avci Akcali & Aslan, 2016) and permanence of learned information is provided (Avci Akcali, 2007; Metin & Oran, 2014), national consciousness is formed (Metin & Oran, 2014), academic success is increased (Danker, 2005; Gokkaya & Yesilbursa, 2009), past events are carried to today and national culture is transferred (Demircioglu & Tokdemir, 2009) sense of belonging develops by forming connection with the past (Douch, 1972; Hawkey, 1995, Sahin 2011).

6.4 Results and discussion of history teachers on application of local history teaching in teaching process

Fourth sub-problem of this study investigated views of history teachers on application of local history teaching. Accordingly, history teachers were asked which activities can be organised under local history teaching in teaching process. History teachers stated that organising trips, project homework, research homework, model making, using libraries, exhibitions, museum visits, historical role playing can be organised under local history teaching. Demircioglu and Tokdemir (2008) has similar results and stated that organising trips (Douch, 1967), museum visits, benefiting from local libraries (Preston, 1969) activities will have important roles for students to learn and create new values. In local history teaching, in addition to introducing historical and cultural environments of the region we live in, activities such as interviews with individuals that witnessed history can be conducted.

In second question, history teachers were asked which methods and techniques can be used in local history teaching. Majority of history teachers stated that trips can be organised. Additionally, teachers stated that methods/techniques such as narrating, argumentation, exhibition, conference, research, interview, seminar and question-answers can be used. In local history teaching, method such as trip-observation (Cengelci, 2013; Douch, 1967; Metin & Oran, 2014, Oner, 2015; Ozturk, 2011), museum visits (Kale, 2011; Preston, 1969) and benefiting from local libraries (Preston, 1969) are used. It is seen that teachers use similar methods/techniques in local history teaching. It can be seen that history teachers especially prefer methods/techniques that activate students. Using these methods/techniques will ensure local history teaching to be more effective.

In third question, history teachers were asked which things should be considered under local history education in the teaching process. History teachers stated that preliminary information should be provided to students, teachers should gain preliminary information, planning should be made, homework should be given to students, making local history teaching motivating, contributing to process, being related with topic, motivating student and complying with purpose. History teachers should take precautions to plan, apply and complete local history teaching based activities according to gains of the class (History Class Curriculum, 2018a). Studies regarding local history teaching on views of history teachers in local history teaching showed similarities with results obtained from this study. It was stated that history teachers should determine a local history working area suitable for topic based on objectives and behaviours of class and inform students how to execute this practice before application (Demircioglu, 2010). Avci Akcali & Aslan (2016) stated that teachers should have theoretical and practical knowledge in local history teaching. Planning activities in local history teaching beforehand, preparing and having preliminary information about these activities for students and teachers will make local history education more effective.

In the fourth question, history teachers were asked what type of problems they experienced with local history education. History teachers expressed problems such as management barriers, procedural issues, financial problems and lack of time. Other studies on this topic had similar results. Metin & Oran (2014) reported that there are problems related with financial problems, curriculum, permission, readiness level of students, lack of documents and records, and lack of personal information in local history. Similarly, Avci Akcali & Aslan (2016) stated that one of the most important factors that can negatively affect use of local history teaching in class is time problem. Aktekin (2010) stated that there are problems such as resource scarcity, time factors, limited opportunities, antiquity interest, narrow regions and oversimplification in local history teaching. Additionally, teachers expressed that they are experiencing problems due to time consuming local history teaching based activity preparation (Demircioglu, 2010). Oner (2015) stated that legal procedures, insufficient class hours due to intense curriculum, lack of interest of managers and teachers are insufficiencies of teachers at application dimension. All these problems cause history teachers to insufficiently include local history teaching and not achieve desired effects of local history education in the teaching process.

Lastly, history teachers were asked to present recommendations to achieve desired efficiency from local history teaching are presented in the table below. History teachers recommended support from school management, support from municipalities for trips, teachers having education on this subject, compliance with curriculum, preparing books about local history teaching. Preston (1969, p. 88) stated that including local history teaching to curriculum will prevent history class being boring; Durlu (1962, p. 11) stated that since local history teaching is direct observation teaching, rather than local history teaching curriculum items, children-based methods that children

show interest should be followed. Isik (2008) stated that historical artefacts in their region should be included as a topic in history curriculum.

Additionally, it was stated that local history should be included in class and teacher should improve (Avci Akcali & Aslan, 2007). Local history teaching includes activities that ensure permanence of knowledge and activities that decrease boring parts of class due to active participation of students. Easier procedures and encouraging teachers to include these activities more is important to achieve desired efficiency from local history teaching.

7. Recommendations

Following recommendations are presented based on obtained results:

1. Prospective teachers should have local history elective classes during undergraduate education to so that history teachers can feel sufficient about local history teaching.
2. In addition for history teachers having sufficient level of knowledge on local history teaching, they need to recognise cultural richness of the geography where they are working.
3. To include local history teaching more, the Ministry of National Education should support these activities and facilitate procedures.
4. School management should help history teachers to include local history activities more and encourage teachers for these activities.
5. To achieve higher efficiency in local history teaching activities, activities in this field should be planned in detailed and all possible situations should be considered.
6. The entertainment aspect of local history teaching activity should be kept behind teaching aspect.

References

- Aktekin, S. (2010). Position and importance of secondary education history in local history. *Education Theories and Practices*, 6(1), 86-105.
- Aktin, K., Karakus, H. & Saglam, H. (2013). Interest and awareness level of Sinop University prospective teachers towards Sinop city historical and cultural artefacts. *The Journal of Academic Social Science Studies (JASSS)*. 6 (7), pp. 37-59.
- Aslan, E. (2000). Definition, development and value of local history. Work: New approaches in history writing: Globalisation and localisation. (Prepared by. Zeynel Abidin Kizilyaprak), p.195-204. İstanbul: Economic and Social History Foundation of Turkey.
- Avci Akcali, A. (2007). *Contribution to local history and history education*. Master's thesis, Dokuz Eylül University Education Science Institute, İzmir.

- Avci Akcali, A. & Aslan, E. (2016). Effect of using local history in history teaching on academic success and historical thinking skills. *GEFAD / GUJGEF*, 36 (2), 375-397.
- Black, J., & MacRaild, D. M. (2000). *Studying history*. Hampshire: Palgrave.
- Buyukozturk, S., Kılıc Cakmakçı, E., Akgun, O. E., Karadeniz, S. & Demirel, F. (2010). *Scientific research methods*. (7. Edition). Ankara: Pegem Academy.
- Calkin, H. L. (1942). Local history: A means of better understanding United States history. *The School Review*. Issue 50. (January 1942).
- Cengelci, T. (2013). Views of social science teachers towards non-class learning, *Education Science in Theory and Practice*, 13(3), pp.1823-1841.
- Cetinkaya, A. & Gulmez, S. T. (2002). *School development model planned school development*. Ankara: Semih Offset Publications.
- Danacioglu, E. (2001a). *Sign of history: A guideline for history right next to us*. İstanbul: History Foundation Yurt Publication.
- Danker, A. C. (2005). *Multicultural social studies: Using local history in the classroom*. New York: Teachers College Press.
- Demircioglu, İ. H. (2010). *Student-centric approach in history teaching*. Ankara: Anı.
- Demircioglu, İ. H. & Tokdemir, M. A. (2008). History teaching while creating values: Purpose, function and content. *Journal of Value Education*, 6 (15), 69-88.
- Douch, R. (1972). Local history. W. H. Burston et al. (Ed.), *Handbook for History Teachers* (p. 75-89). London: Methuen Education Ltd.
- Durlu, R. (1962). Observation and nearby dorm. *Elementary School Journal*, s. 507, Ankara: M.E.B. Publication Director.
- Erkus, A. (2009). *Scientific research methods of behavioural science*. Ankara: Seekin publication.
- Finberg, H. P. R. (1967). Local history. In Finberg, H.P.R., and Skipp, V.H.T., *Local history objective and pursuit* (25-44). Newton Abbot: David and Charles Publishers Ltd.
- Gokkaya, A. K. & Yesilbursa, C. C. (2009). Effect of using historical places in social science teaching on academic success. *Turkish Journal of Educational Sciences*, 7(2), 483-506.
- Hawkey, K. (1995). History teaching and the council of Europe. *Teaching History*, 78, 17-19.
- Hoskins, W. G. (1984). *Local history in England*. New York: Addison Wesley Longman Limited.
- Isik, H. (2008). Effects of relating elementary school history topics with local history on student success. *Journal of International Social Research*, 1(4), 290-310.
- Ilyasoglu, A. (2001). When meeting with local history groups: Topics, issues. Funda Celebi (Ed), *Local history, city, civil Development: Local history group experience* (p. 37-42). İstanbul: Economic and Social History Foundation of Turkey.
- Islamoglu, H. (2009). *Research methods in social science*. İstanbul: Beta publications.

- Kale, Y. (2011). Museums and historical places in history education. M. Safran (Ed.), *How to teach history? Special teaching methods for history teachers* (p. 195-203). İstanbul: New People.
- Mainstone, M., & Bryant, M. (1972). The use of museums and historical sites. In Burston, W. H., and Green, C. W. (ed.) *Handbook for History Teachers* (163-172) London: Methuen Educational Ltd.
- MEB (2018a). *Secondary education history class curriculum (9, 10 and 11 Grades)*.
- Metcalf, F. D., & Downey, M. T. (1982). Local history in American education. *The Local Historian*, 15(4), 204-211.
- Metin, B. & Oran, M. (2014). In-class local history activities of elementary school social science teachers: Usak city case. *Usak University Journal of Education Research*, 7(1), 204-216.
- Oner, G. (2015). Analysis of social science teachers regarding "out-of-school history education". *Journal of Turkish History Education*, 4 (1), 89-121.
- Ozturk, M. (2011). Space perception skills. M. Safran (Ed.), *How to teach history? Special teaching methods for history teachers* (p. 184-194). İstanbul: New People.
- Philips, R. (2003). History, citizenship and identity. *Teaching history*, December 36 (2), 37- 41.
- Plymouth, J. H. B. (1933). The teaching of local history. *History*, XVIII (69), 1-10.
- Preston, G. (1969). The value of local history in the school curriculum. *Teaching History*, Volume 1, 87-91.
- Quest, R. E. (2006). *The infusion of local history into the New York state eleventh grade united states history curriculum*. (Unpublished doctorate dissertation). Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania.
- Rogers, A. (1977). *Approaches to local history*. New York: Longman.
- Slater, J. (1995). *Teaching history in the New Europe*. London: Cassell.
- Sonmez, V. & Alacapinar, F.(2014). *Sampled scientific research methods*. (3. Edition) Ankara: Ani Publication.
- Tunc Sahin, C. (2011). Effect of local history applications on success and student products. *Journal of International Social Research*, 4(16), 453-463.
- TTKB (2007). *Secondary education 9th grade history class curriculum*. <http://ttkb.meb.gov.tr/ogretmen/index.php>.
- TTKB (2008a). *Secondary education 10th grade history class curriculum*. <http://ttkb.meb.gov.tr/ogretmen/index.php>.
- TTKB (2008b). *Secondary education modern Turkish and world history class curriculum*. <http://ttkb.meb.gov.tr/ogretmen/index.php>.
- TTKB (2009). *Secondary education 11th grade history class curriculum*. <http://ttkb.meb.gov.tr/ogretmen/index.php>.
- TTKB (2010). *Secondary education Republic of Turkey revolution history and Kemalism class curriculum*. <http://ttkb.meb.gov.tr/ogretmen/index.php>.
- Yildirim, A. & Simsek, H. (2008). *Qualitative research methods in social science*. Ankara: Seckin Publication.

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